

LANGUAGE AND CULTURE IN ENGLISH CLASSROOMS: GREETINGS, WAYS OF EXPRESSING POLITENESS

Yakubjanova Ruzikhan Mirkomil qizi

Teacher of Andijan State Foreign Languages Institute

Xudoyberdiyeva Muxlisaxon Lutfullo qizi

Student of Andijan State Foreign Languages Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7867197>

Annotation: This article gives information about greetings, ways of expressing politeness in different cultures.

Key words: expressing politeness, greetings, English classroom, culture, politeness.

Introduction. Language and culture share a fascinating relationship and it's hard to teach one without touching upon the other. That's why the issue of culture shouldn't be ignored by either teachers or students in a language classroom.

English culture is based on the cultures of the English-speaking countries like Britain and USA. According to Johnson (2009), there is no way in which someone can learn a language without accepting the culture that comes with it. Therefore, as one learns the language he/she is forced to accept the cultures of it.

Teaching culture is an integral part of Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages (TESOL). In order to communicate clearly and effectively in English, students must have knowledge of the language's vocabulary, grammar, when and how to use them appropriately (function), and the corresponding body language.

Essentially, incorporating culture into a language lesson changes it from being purely an academic subject (like maths or science) to more of a hobby that can connect with students on a more personal level.

"Language is culture. There is no way to wrap your mind around the culture of a country if you don't speak the language. Our minds don't create words, words shape our minds our cognition, our way to apprehend the world." - Arnaud, Albania language schools.

Word use, speech patterns, tone – all of these can affect the meaning and reaction to a sentence. Therefore, anyone who's mastered all of the complexities of their target language is likely to get a warm welcome in their host country! Overall, culture has a valuable place in the classroom, simply because a language can't be truly grasped without at least a simple understanding of the culture.

Hello, Bonjour, Hola, Salaam, Guten tag, Hello, Здравствуйте! It's the first word you learn in any new language, the basic sign of welcome that shows your intent to talk to someone. Most likely, you learned the basic English greetings before you even started investing time in your language skills. But if you want to make the most of your first impression, there are a ton of more colorful ways to say "hello". When people meet, it is a common practice to shake hands. A handshake generally lasts for a few seconds, which gives enough time to say "Pleased to meet you".

These ways of greeting people are used at different times of the day. Whether you speak with a regular customer, colleagues or new neighbors, these phrases are effective to start the ball rolling.

The greetings change depending on the time of the day. For example, “Good morning” is generally used from 5:00 a.m. to 12:00 p.m. whereas “Good afternoon” time is from 12:00 p.m. to 6:00 p.m. “Good evening” is often used after 6 p.m. or when the sun goes down. To show your respect, you can also add the person’s last name to your greeting words. Usually, native English speakers tend to be more informal even in business communication and use the person’s first name after the salutation:

- Good morning, Mr. Houston
- Good afternoon, Ms. Partridge
- Good morning, Tom
- Good evening, Kelly

It is also common to say “Good morning, sir/madam” when greeting someone in a formal situation whose name is unknown. This is often heard by staff talking to customers in shops, restaurants and hotels. A brief afterword A well-chosen “hello” sets the tone for any conversation, whether talking to a close friend or someone you barely know. Don’t be afraid to try out these new expressions in your daily communication. Armed with these words and phrases, you can start almost any conversation off in a more vibrant and fluent way.

Politeness is the practical application of good manners or etiquette so as not to offend others. It is a culturally defined phenomenon, and therefore what is considered polite in one culture can sometimes be quite rude or simply eccentric in another cultural context. While the goal of politeness is to refrain from behaving in an offensive way so as not to offend others and make all people feel relaxed and comfortable with one another, these culturally defined standards at times may be manipulated.

Negative politeness: Making a request less infringing, such as "If you don't mind..." or "If it isn't too much trouble..."; respects a person's right to act freely. In other words, deference. There is a greater use of indirect speech acts. Also considered a part of being assertive.

Non-assertive politeness: when a person refrains from making a comment or asserting their beliefs during a discussion so as to remain polite to others present. Also when a person goes along with a decision made by someone else so as not to appear impolite.

Assertive politeness: when a person offers their opinion in a positive and constructive way to be assistive and helpful during an interaction. Or to refrain from agreeing with something they do not actually agree with in a way that does not offend others.

Positive politeness: Seeks to establish a positive relationship between parties; respects a person's need to be liked and understood. Direct speech acts, swearing and flouting Grice's maxims can be considered aspects of positive politeness because:

- they show an awareness that the relationship is strong enough to cope with what would normally be considered impolite (in the popular understanding of the term);
- they articulate an awareness of the other person's values, which fulfills the person's desire to be accepted.

Some cultures seem to prefer one of these kinds of politeness over the other. In this way politeness is culturally bound.

To conclude, culture holds an essential role when teaching language. Making room for culture within the classroom will make sure that students can fully grasp the complexity of their

chosen language while also enjoying and embracing the learning process.

References:

1. Agbaglo, E. (2017). The use of politeness strategies in the analysis and discussion sections of English researcher articles. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 7(9):30-42.
2. Alfikri, M. (2021). The importance of communication strategies in implementing the dissemination of development innovations: A case study of the communications and Information Office of North Sumatra. *Technium Social Sciences journal*, Vol. 24, pp 228-234.
3. Al-hindawi, F.H. & Alkhazaali, M.A.R. (2016). A critique of politeness theories. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 6(8), p.1537.
4. Beach, D.N., 1980. *The Shona & Zimbabwe 900-1850: An Outline of Shona History*. London: Heinemann Educational Publishers.
5. Brown, P. & Levinson, S.C. (1987). *Politeness: some universals in language use*. Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.
6. Caulfield, J. (2020). *A guide to ethnography*. Amsterdam: Jack Caulfield Publishers.